

Artificial Intelligence and Sentience: A Study of Holli Mintzer's Short Story "Tomorrow is waiting"

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Abstract:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has gained prominence globally due to its ability to ease human effort. Artificial intelligence is the intelligence exhibited by machines to accomplish goals ascribed by humans. Today popular search engines, creative tools and video games display the power of artificial intelligence. With this unprecedented development comes the question if artificial intelligence would supplant human beings. Among diverse aspects, sentience is a parameter generally attributed to humans and regarded as a differentiator between humans and artificial intelligence. However, with the rapid advancement in artificial intelligence, literature has started to represent the pros and cons of Artificial Intelligence. Holli Mintzer's short story "Tomorrow is Waiting" offers relevant insights to address a futuristic world where Anji, the protagonist, might have accidentally created a sentient machine. This paper aims to understand the repercussions of sentience in machines by closely reading the short story. It seeks to understand the implications of science fiction AI narratives.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Sentience, Human Values, Self

Introduction:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is represented in science fiction. The short story "Tomorrow is Waiting" can be considered a science fiction story where artificial intelligence's potential dangers and apprehensions are portrayed. The story depicts the dream of creating a sentient robotic AI. Artificial Intelligence in science fiction narratives is meant for a human audience. The real technological limitations are ignored to depict machines as humanlike or fully autonomous. Isabella Hermann in "Artificial Intelligence in Fiction: Between Narratives and Metaphors" mentions the problems involved in taking Artificial Intelligence in fiction literally. As fictionalized narratives represent AI which are far more advanced than what humans have made in reality, science fiction narratives at times present unrealistic depictions of the implications of AI. From this perspective, artificial intelligence represented in the story is to be taken only as a fictionalized account. However, the fears and hopes brought by AI fiction may impact the development of AI. This is the reason why AI narratives, according to the author, may mislead the audience about AI. The mere presence of AI in fiction is not intended to showcase the implications of technology. Rather, the social issues associated with AI is represented through stories. At times Artificial Intelligence in fiction is way more developed than reality. The robots presented are "anthropomorphized" and made humanlike which does not match with the real advancements (Hermann 320). Hermann does not agree that machines can think autonomously and the creation of autonomous machines "reinforces existing misconceptions about the agency or autonomy of AI" (320). Though sentient AI is created accidentally, critics claim that machines follow the interests of the human creator. Whether Artificial Intelligence is seen as influencing the vested human

interest should be the point of discussion. In stories, robots are similar to humans, replicating their actions, words and intentions. Machines with humanlike capabilities are built to fulfil the demands of the narrative.

Science-fictional AI is a dramatic element that makes a perfect antagonist, enemy, victim or even hero, because it can be fully adjusted to the necessities of the story. (322). This is the reason why authors create sentient AI which supersedes human capabilities. The story "Tomorrow is Waiting" projects the story of Anji or Anjali who pursues a career in artificial intelligence. She is a hard-working student who works on a project to build a machine that possesses artificial intelligence. The prominent point of discussion is the creation of artificial intelligence, that can pass all tests and prove superior to the human brain. There is a presumption that artificial intelligence cannot supersede the human brain. However, this story subverts the notion of superiority of the human brain. Learning how to create cripple-bots that can work in traffic signals and learning the basic basics of AI programming, Anjali tries hard to pass the examination along with creating a good project for her career. To create an artificial intelligence which can mimic a character, she selects Kermit the frog. The availability of a plethora of footage on TV encourages her to undertake Kermit the Frog as an object of interpretation and creation of character. The two characters- Anji and Brian- get puzzled witnessing the robot's advancements. It starts generating its code and advances enough to play the banjo. It starts writing its code which startles Anjali. The robot develops to a stage where it mimics and creates jokes which seems an impossibility. It is at this stage that Brian thinks they have accidentally created sentient AI. Machines are supposed not to have emotional intelligence. The sentient AI, which Brian refers to in the story, is capable of missing a

friend. Kermit the Frog creates his songs, changes the lyrics according to his suitability and performs on his banjo.

The title of the story is quite relevant to the sentient AI. It sings the song "Tomorrow is Waiting for Me", with the presumption that the next day is inevitable. The robot uttering and making lyrics for itself is an indication of a conscious being. The author presents the robot as a conscious being capable of using language to express ideas. A robotic object capable of creating and using language to express ideas draws attention to Rene Descartes who considered language as a tool to express ideas. For Thomas Hobbes, language helps to arrange thoughts. It is the way to organise the sensory impressions. For Thomas Hobbes, the ability of reasoning, lets the mind know about the labels attached to them. The human characters are surprised and shocked at the sudden display of use of language by the robots.

The author Holli Mintzer creates the robotic character as a possessor of consciousness and the ability to think for itself. The machine recalls that it used to be a puppet frog. It realizes its transformation into a robot frog and eventually into a real frog. The recognition of the existence of reality by the robot is evidence of its sentience. The robot begins to have consciousness about itself as an individual entity with an identity. The assumption that the frog can think is an impossibility. According to the article, "Unlearning Descartes: Sentient AI is a Political Problem". Gordon Hall argues that artificial intelligence systems cannot be considered as conscious entities as the person who created them shall always be held accountable for the actions of the robot. Though Kermit the Frog speaks independently, its language aligns with the creator's inputs.

In the story, certain characters question whether Kermit the Frog is a hoax or a sentient AI. What may be considered sentient is subjected to interpretations. Though narratives such as "Tomorrow is Waiting" create machines that can move, talk and act independently, a resort to understanding sentience is necessary. The invention of self-moving devices can be traced back to the 17th century. When the castle of Rudolf II of Prague, possessed collections of items which were self-moving. Gordon Hall assumes that Rene Descartes must have visited the city of Prague where such collections were displayed. Descartes' formulation of the mind is based on his understanding of the living bodies. In *Discourses on Method*, the human body possesses a rational soul created by God. The power of God is considered far superior to machines which operate on their own accord. Descartes' distinction between the human mind and man-made clocks and mills concludes with the human body being attributed with superior powers. A rational soul is capable of having doubts, denials and affirmations. The sensory perceptions must be active to

function. The prime differentiation between human beings and machines is that the former is capable of displaying sentience and consciousness. The story vehemently rejects perceptions about machines which was previously thought. Sentience, attributed only to humans, is not a reality today. However, a peep into the futuristic developments makes the story intriguing. According to Hall, sentient AI is a distant reality if the Cartesian viewpoint is taken into account. Thomas Hobbes deals with the problem of the mind. His idea of the mind is significant as his notion of thinking is similar to computation. Thomas Hobbes' idea of ratiocination in the mind which facilitates subtraction and addition is a form of computation. The operation of the mind, in this sense, has similarities with the AI.

According to Thomas Hobbes, for the mind to work, sensory impressions and memory play a crucial role. Experience impacts the way the mind interprets things. In AI, apart from the algorithm, collection and levelling data is necessary. The story seems to present the machine displaying a mind acting autonomously. The machines are not capable of replicating the complications of the human mind. If when it does in fiction, the characters do not seem to be pleased about the outcome. Thomas Hobbes' idea of the mind shall also problematize the idea of personhood in machines. In the story, the robot tries to identify itself as a person capable of doing wonders. Sophisticated sentient AI shall bring in the problem of personhood. Taking Thomas Hobbes's *Leviathan* into account, one is considered a person when words and actions are presented as his own. Whether this can be an attribute to be considered as a person is questionable. The story makes an imaginary reference to robots trying to behave as persons. The robot impersonates human beings and tries to establish its own identity. It makes an attempt to become more humanlike, which the creator Anji seems to be worrying about. Holli Mintzer's short story depicts a world where sentient AI seems to be a possibility. If a sentient AI is created there seems to be a problem in perceiving the issue of identity and personhood. As a science fiction narrative, the story vividly projects the problems which an advanced AI can cause in society.

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